

Redhorse Bend Project, Sandusky County (41.36625, -83.10390)

Since construction in 2021, the constrained floodplain connection design of the Redhorse Bend Project has limited its capacity to receive water and retain nutrients. River water inflows through the streambank cuts only during extreme high flow events of >12,000 cubic feet per second (cfs). Inflow during typical high flow events (8,000–10,000 cfs) is restricted to the eastern ditch. In 2024, these design limitations were exacerbated by drought conditions, resulting in lower nutrient filtration in 2024 than in 2023, along with the Project's runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 55 acres restored wetland with two distinct features: a set of floodplain wetland pools that connect to each other in series but have limited connectivity to water inputs from the river itself; and a single pool meant to capture separate ditch water. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event in which the USGS gage (Sandusky River near Fremont OH - 04198000) reaches 12,000 cfs, as this is when researchers estimate the river flows through the cut banks into the set of floodplain wetland pools. However, when the Sandusky River reaches a lower flow threshold of 3,000 cfs, water first enters a ditch and then the series of minor pools. At another location, a single pool intended to capture water from a separate drainage ditch, in fact, mostly receives inputs from rainwater and surface water runoff from an adjacent meadow.

Nutrient Retention

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar floodplain wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Lower the berm between Pool 6 and the partner-managed highway drainage ditch. Or, if connectivity between the ditch and pool cannot be improved, a location closer to the river might be an alternative to Pool 6 to capture more upland wet meadow drainage.
- Make the ABC pools deeper, with lower berms between them and the main pools, to increase the functionality of the Project by increasing overall site hydrologic connectivity, stormwater storage, and nutrient storage capacity for flooding events rather than just precipitation events.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.